

An Empirical Study on the Effect of Retail Service Quality Attributes on the Consumer Buying Decision - With Reference to Moustache

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Abstract: The study was been conceptualized to study the effect of retail service quality on the consumer decision making process for a brand selection. Therefore, to create a distinct position in the marketplace, retailers are focusing on retail service quality that gives a competitive advantage to the company. Exploratory factor analysis was run to understand the retail service quality factors in fashion retail market with relevance to the brand, Moustache. Six components were extracted through Varimax method and rotated component matrix, namely *store presentation/display, convenient facilities, problem solving, temperature, store layout* and *personal interaction*. For regression analysis, the hypothesis developed for the research were perceptual service quality of the fashion retail store influences the perceptual quality of the brand and different dimensions of retail service quality influences significantly the perceptual quality of the brand. Significant relationship between perceptual quality of the retail store and perceptual quality of the brand has been established. Cluster analysis was done first by hierarchical method to deduce number of clusters which can be formed, and then the data was further processed through Ward Method in K-Means Cluster Method. Four differentiating segments were concluded with discrete characteristics. The study also attempted to understand the influence of three factors, store outlet/format, assistance and exclusive range, on customer preference. Utility of all the eight options was calculated through conjoint analysis according to the preferences of the customers.

Keywords: Fashion Retail Market, Retail Service quality, Conjoint, Cluster, Regression, Factor Analysis

I. Introduction

The retail industry is largely diverse with presence of small retails in developing countries but are largely dominated by big firms. With growth in working population, brand consciousness and higher incomes in India, a

smooth transition is reflected in the retail market which is estimated to reach US\$950 billion by 2018 (Sehgal & Khanna, 2017). Activities involving the selling of goods and services for personal or business use, directly to the consumers via activities which ensures maximum value derived by the consumer is known as retailing (Koul & Mishra, 2013). The retailers are trying to come up with new strategies in response to changing buying behavior of the consumers with the objective to make customers come back to the store. In this regard emphasis should be put on the store characteristics as it influences the consumer shopping behavior (Nishanov & Ahunjonov, 2016).

In the retail industry, high growth rate has been experienced in the developed countries, while it is growing exponentially in the developing countries, It is expected that the overall retail industry in India will reach to 1.3 trillion USD by 2020. Rise in the demand of readymade and western outfits is growing at 40-45% annually. The awareness among the Indian consumers about the latest fashion, innovative usage of the store space and their expectations for quality products that meet the global standards are increasing. (Mehta & Chugan, 2014).

A business model in a retail world would mean the products and the services offered by the retailer and the way it chooses to communicate its offerings to the consumers (Azeem & Sharma, 2015). In the fashion industry, the similarity of products and competition in the market force each segment to enhance the desirability of products by utilizing visual merchandising. It's high time for the retailers to change their mindset to efficiently compete and match up to the foreign competitors in terms of visual merchandising in order to be successful (Singh & Mhatre, 2016).

In India, increase in the purchasing power is seen with increase in urbanization. A gradual revolution is witnessed in the shopping scenario in India with an increase in growth of the retail industry (Ghosh, Tripathi, & Kumar, 2010). The apparel retail environment is undergoing continuous changes at a more frequent pace. While shopping apparel the consumers become impulsive and fickle minded. Demand for new products and pressurize the retailers to become more pro-active in order to keep pace with the dynamic nature of the apparel retail environment (Preez, Visser, & Noordwyk, 2008).

Service Quality: Quality can also be defined as the totality of features and characteristics of a product or services that bear on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs. "A service is any activity or benefit that one party can offer to the another that is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything" (Kotler P. , 1999). As defined by (Parasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml, SERVQUAL: A multiple- Item Scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality, 1988), service quality is "the differences between customer expectations and perceptions of service"

In today's retail environment, one of the objectives is to create a superior experience for the customers. The retail environment has a great impact on the emotion of the consumers' and their satisfaction level (Hussain & Ali, 2015). The focus of the retail businesses should be on the preferences of the consumers and factors that influence their purchase decision. High complexity is involved in planning the layout of a retail store outlet. The core objective is maximization of sales with customer satisfaction and minimization of cost (Singh, Katiyar, & Verma, 2014).

Merchandise value and *variety, frontline staff and interior store environment* are independent variables that help in predicting customer loyalty (Terblanche & Boshoff, 2006). *Brand* carried by the store, friendly personnel *price, quality* and selection of *merchandise* are the key retail clothing store attributes.

Store ambience directly influences the consumers' shopping behavior. Stores having *attractive, fashionable, stylish decorations, lightings and maintained temperature* have a positive influence on the shopping behavior of the consumers (Moye & Giddings, 2002).

The complexity in the process of making purchase decisions is due to the inseparability of the services and products offered by the retailers. Hence, it is very important to understand the importance of the store attributes in the process of selection of the store by the consumers for purchase of products (Ghosh, Tripathi, & Kumar, 2010). The thoughts and beliefs of the consumers associated with the store over a period of time influence their shopping behavior at that store (Imran, Ghani, & Rehman). Sometimes the purchase decisions are influenced by factors like *physical surroundings* and *purchasing power of an individual* (Shamout, 2016). According to this study, the widely known key influencers behind the formation of the purchase intentions of the consumers are *service quality* and *customer satisfaction* (Baker & Taylor, 1994).

II. Literature Review

Store Image

In the study, the combination of the perception of the consumers' about a store based on salient attributes can be defined as a *store image* (Gundala R. R., 2010). According to the researcher, the store image comprises of characteristics attributes that help the customers to differentiate a store from other stores by making them feel differently. The intangible attributes of the store play a very important part in making the impression of the store in the minds of the consumers (Ghosh, Tripathi, & Kumar, 2010). Store image acts as an evaluation criterion on deciding the selection of a retail store (Varley, 2005). The researcher tried to find out the factors that influences the store image of discount and speciality stores. The factors are *Atmosphere, Convenience, Facilities, Institutional, Merchandise, Promotion, Sales personnel appearance,*

Sales personnel interaction and Service (Preez, Visser, & Noordwyk, 2008). According to the researcher the dimension of the store image comprises of store image dimensions: *a store's merchandise, service, clientele, physical facilities, convenience, promotion, store atmosphere, institutional factors and post-transaction satisfaction* (Lindquist, 1974). It has been concluded by the researcher that the image of the retail store can be divided into *price, product assortment, product quality in-store service, location and social experience* (Tariq, Afzal, & Fiaz, 2016). According to the researcher, store image is the combination of *objective attributes and subjective attributes*. Objective attributes include *size, store hours, location and subjective attributes include friendliness of employees, attractiveness of store décor* (Kasulis & Lasch, 1981). In the study, the researcher found out that image of the store is a very important component for the success in apparel retail in the challenging and ever-changing environment marked by intense competition (Preez, Visser, & Noordwyk, 2008).

Store Attributes

In the study, it has been found out that the consumers are affected more by the non-price factors, that is the store attributes like *merchandise assortment, store atmosphere, store sales personnel* etc. than the price factors. Six factors were identified in the study namely *store ambience, store pricing policy, sales assistance, store promotion, store attractiveness, and store convenience* as the factors that influence the purchase decisions of the consumers at an organized retail store. Amongst these the most and the last important factors are *sales assistance and store ambience* respectively (Sehgal & Khanna, 2017). It has been concluded by the researcher that *store patronage* is affected by *layout and convenience* (Baker, Parasuraman, Grewal, & Voss, 2002). According to the study, store attributes play a very important role in the process of store selection. Three major factors influencing the shopping behavior of the consumer identified by the researcher are *Services, Merchandise and Convenience, and Store Atmospherics* (Ghosh, Tripathi, & Kumar, 2010). According to the researcher, by manipulating the store attributes associated with the store image, retailers can create a positive and unique image of the store as perceived by the consumers (Preez, Visser, & Noordwyk, 2008).

Service Quality

Five service quality dimensions were identified by the researchers (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, SERVQUAL-A Multiple-Item Scale for Measuring Consumers Perception of Service Quality, 1988) to assess the service quality namely, *Tangibles* (Physical facilities, equipment and appearance of personnel), *Reliability* (Ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately), *Responsiveness* (Willingness to help customers and provide prompt services), *Assurance* (Knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence), *Empathy* (Caring, individualized attention the firm provides its customers). (Cronin & Taylor, 1994) on the basis of SERVQUAL model has developed SERVPREF scale using the same dimensions as SERVQUAL model namely, *Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy* to measure the perceived service quality that leads to satisfaction. Rapid changes in the retail environment were characterized by intensive competition and increase in the demand of the customers whose expectations have become greater than before in respect to their consumption experiences. The basic strategy in retailing for creating a competitive advantage is to deliver high quality of service. In the study (Dabholkar, Thorpe, & Rentz, 1996) developed a scale namely, Retail Service Quality Scale to measure service quality in a retail environment that includes five dimensions namely, *Physical aspects-Store appearance and convenience of store layout, Reliability-Retailer keeps its promises and "does things right", Personal interaction-Associates are courteous, helpful and they inspire confidence and trust from the customer., Problem solving-Associates are trained to handle professional problems, such as customer complaints, returns and exchanges. Policy-Operating hours, payment options, store charge cards, parking and so forth.*

Customer Service

According to the study, interactions with the employees help in creating trust, relationship, customer loyalty, positive word of mouth and enhancement of customer cooperation (Terblanche N. S., 2017). According to the study, excellent customer service can be provided by the retailers to differentiate their offerings, gain competitive advantage and build customer loyalty (Grewal & Levy, 2007). In the study, it was been concluded that a vital role is played by the sales personnel in the course of creating and maintaining relationships between a buyer and a seller. According to the study, the responsibility of the sales personnel is to identify the needs of the buyer, satisfy them and provide further support services (Plank, Belonex, & Newell, 2008). According to the study, ethical behavior of the sales personnel is very important because the front line staff is considered to represent the image of the organization in their actions (Zia, Luqman, & Akram, 2016). According to the study, consumers usually patronize stores having experienced sales personnel who are approachable, supportive, kind, amicable, and attentive (Gundala R. R., 2010). According to the study, knowledgeable and helpful sales personnel have a positive impact on the perception of the consumers' about the image of the store (Hu & Jasper, 2006).

The researcher tried to find out that in order to enhance the customer retention, good service to the customers must be kept at priority to drive profitability (Ghosh, Tripathi, & Kumar, 2010). According to the study, after sales services is one of the marketing strategies which is designed to meet the objective of creating a brand ultimately resulting in brand loyalty (Shivalingegowda & C, 2013). In the study, the researcher tried to find out the attributes relating to the service

expected by the customers which included *returns, refunds, alterations, in-store credit, helpful suggestions* and *honest sales assistants* (Visser, Du, & Noordwyk, 2006).

Store Design and Display (Presentation)

According to the study, well-designed or attractive retail merchandise displays may increase the value of the goods perceived by the consumers and contribute to increased sales (Lam, 2005). According to the study, consumers are persuaded by attractive display of the merchandise to make purchases out of impulsiveness (Abratt, Goodey, & Stephen, 1990). In the study, the researcher found out that effective display of merchandise creates a great impact on the purchase decisions made by the customers and builds a positive image of the store in the minds of the customers' that results in attention, interest, desire and action on the customer's part (Mehta & Chugan, 2014). According to the study, retailers objective is to motivate the customers to make planned, unplanned and impulse purchase by attracting and guiding them to spot the merchandise they desire. *Display of merchandise* on the mannequin also helps the consumers to visualize particular outfit on them. *Promotional items, eye-catching displays and visuals* have a great potential to have an impact on the consumer behavior. Creative and inspiring window displays pull the customers to the store. Making sudden changes in the window displays may not increase the sales immediately but can have a positive impact on the image of the store in the long run. (Singh & Mhatre, 2016). According to the study, attractive displays help the people to walk into the store and look around by drawing attention to the offerings. Use of window displays, especially for new products increase the sales of the store. It has been found that an important role is played by the promotional signage in establishing the image of the store. In-store displays force customers to give a look at the products which are displayed in a creative way, thus having an influence on the purchase decision (Ventrivel & Prasad, 2016). In the study, it has been found out by the researcher that in-store and window displays influence the consumer shopping behavior by encouraging them to spend more time in the store and purchase the product (Hefer & Cant, 2013).

Store Atmosphere

In the study, it has been concluded by the researcher that *cleanliness, lightning, display and scent* have a significantly positive influence on the purchase intention of the consumers, whereas *music* and *color* minimally impact the purchase intention of the consumers whereas the *temperature* maintained in the retail store has hardly any impact on the consumers' shopping behavior (Hussain & Ali, 2015). It has been concluded by the researcher that the consumers' create an impression in his/her mind by looking at the level of the cleanliness in the store and overall affects the feeling of the customer towards a particular retail outlet and makes them stay for a longer period of time (Yun & Good, 2007). (Yüksel, 2009) proposed that colour has a significant impact on the perception of the consumers towards the merchandise offered. Elements such as colour and lightning have an immediate impact on the consumers' buying decision process. Music, lightning, flooring and smell creates a unique shopping experience for the consumers. According to the study, store atmosphere strongly influences the image of the store and behavior of the consumers. (Ventrivel & Prasad, 2016). According to the study, the store atmosphere helps to determine the store image by not only guaranteeing convenience and comfort but also having an influencing on the purchase decision. In the study, it has been found out by the researcher that store atmosphere has significant effect on emotion of the customer and purchase decisions taken by them. Therefore customer emotions has an noteworthy effect on purchase decisions. Thus, customer emotions act as a mediating element in the relationship between store atmosphere and purchase decisions. (Madjid, 2013).

III. Research Objectives

Primary Objective:

- To study the effect of various retail service attributes on the consumer behaviour of Brand choice w.r.t. Moustache.

Secondary Objectives:

- To identify the various retail service attributes affecting the consumer buying decision.
- To study the influence on the perceptual quality of the store on perceptual quality of the brand, influence on retail service quality factors on the perceptual quality of the store and perceptual quality of the brand.
- To segment the market into distinct clusters based on retail service quality factors.
- To study the preferences of the customers based on utility of various options among combination different retail attributes.

IV. Research Methodology

Research Design

The research design of the study is partly *exploratory* and partly *conclusive* in nature. The primary objective of exploratory research is to provide insights into and an understanding of marketing phenomena. Exploratory research is meaningful in any situation where the researcher does not have enough understanding to proceed with the research

project. The objective of conclusive research is to test specific hypotheses and examine relationships (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research - An Applied Approach, 2006). In this research the researchers tried to explore the area of retail service quality in terms of store attributes and examine relationships. In the study, the researchers tried to use both primary and secondary data. Primary Data is originated by the researcher for the specific purpose of addressing the problem at hand (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research-An Applied Approach, 2006).

Data Collecting Tool: As a data collecting tool, the researchers have used, *structured non-disguised questionnaire* with both open and close ended questions. A Questionnaire is called a scheduled interview form or measuring instrument including formalized set of questions for obtaining information from respondents (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research-An Applied Approach, 2006). Non-disguised approach is a direct approach in which purpose of the project is disclosed to the respondents or is otherwise obvious to them from the questions asked. The reason for asking structured questions is to improve the consistency of the wording used in doing the study at different places which increases the reliability of the study by ensuring that every respondent is asked the same question (Nargundkar, 2004) and the survey instrument was used to collect data through personal interviews. *Thirty, five point Liker Scale* with a rating of 1-5 where 5 is strong agreement with the statement, 4 is agreement with the statement, 3 is neither agreement nor disagreement, 2 is disagreement and 1 is strong disagreement with the statements were formed on the factors and the respondents were asked for their opinion and responses.

Type and Sources of Data: Both, primary and secondary data are used in the research work. The primary data has been collected from the customers of the brand while the secondary data include, literatures of different authors and store sales data.

Sampling Process: A sample is any part of the fully defined population. To make accurate inferences, the sample has to be representative. The researcher has used *non-probabilistic* sampling technique, along with *convenience* sampling. For this research non-probability sampling has been taken, as there is no available sample frame. In a non-probabilistic sampling technique all the individual samples do not have the equal chances of being selected by the researcher. A non-probability sampling technique that attempts to obtain a sample of convenient elements. The selection of sampling units is left primarily to the interviewer. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique where subjects are selected because of their convenient accessibility and proximity to the researcher (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research - An Applied Approach, 2006). When population elements are selected for inclusion in the sample based on the ease of access, it can be called convenience sampling (Kothari, 2004). It involves picking up of any available set of respondents convenient for the researcher to use (Nargundkar, 2004). In this research, all the men wearing denim jeans in Kolkata comprised the population of this study.

Sample size: This refers to the number of items to be selected from the universe to constitute a sample (Kothari, 2004). Sample size is the number of observations in a sample. A sampling plan is a detailed outline of which measurements will be taken at what times, on which material, in what manner, and by whom. 150 respondents were selected as samples to carry out the study.

Data Analysis Tool: Data Analysis is the process of systematically applying statistical and/or logical techniques to describe and illustrate, condense and recap, and evaluate data. Software used is and SPSS 23. Statistical tools used are Factor analysis and reliability test, Correlation & Regression, Cluster and Conjoint Analysis.

V. Findings and Analysis:

Validity Test: Validity of an assessment is the degree to which it measures what it is supposed to measure. Construct validity defines how well a test or experiment measures up to its claims. After the questions were formed to ask the respondents, opinion of experts were taken into consideration to measure the construct validity.

Factor Analysis:

Factor analysis allows an examination of the potential interrelationships among a number of variables and the evaluation of the underlying reasons for these. Factor analysis is a statistical analysis which denotes a class of procedures primarily used for data reduction and summarization and is used to reduce a large number of variables, most of which are correlated and which are reduced to such a level where maximum variation of the factors is explained. The researcher has followed Varimax Method in Factor Analysis which is a change of coordinates used in principal component analysis and factor analysis that maximizes the sum of the variances of the squared loadings (squared correlations between variables and factors).

The Key Statistics Associated with Factor Analysis are as Follows: *Bartlett's test of sphericity* is a test statistic used to examine the hypothesis that the variables are uncorrelated in the population. In other words, the population correlation matrix is an identity matrix; each variable correlates perfectly with itself ($r = 1$) but has no correlation with the other variables ($r = 0$). *Communality* is the amount of variance a variable shares with all the other variables being considered. This is also the

proportion of variance explained by the common factors. A *correlation matrix* is a lower triangle matrix showing the simple correlations, *r*, between all possible pairs of variables included in the analysis. The diagonal elements, which are all 1, are usually omitted. The *Eigen value* represents the total variance explained by each factor. *Factor loadings* are simple correlations between the variables and the factors. A *factor loading plot* is a plot of the original variables using the factor loadings as coordinates. A *factor matrix* contains the factor loadings of all the variables on all the factors extracted. *Factor scores* are composite scores estimated for each respondent on the derived factors. The percentage of the total variance attributed to each factor

Bartlett's test of sphericity can be used to test the null hypothesis that the variables are uncorrelated in the population; in other words, the population correlation matrix is an identity matrix. In an identity matrix, all the diagonal terms are 1, and all off-diagonal terms are 0. The test statistic for sphericity is based on a chi-square transformation of the determinant of the correlation matrix. A large value of the test statistic will favour the rejection of the null hypothesis. If this hypothesis cannot be rejected, then the appropriateness of factor analysis should be questioned. For this data, Bartlett's test is highly significant ($p < 0.05$ as $p = 0.000$), and therefore factor analysis is appropriate (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research-An Applied Approach, 2006). It has been suggested by (Coakes & Ong, 2011) that if the Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant, and if the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure is greater than 0.6, then factor analysis is appropriate.

Another useful statistic is the Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy. This index compares the magnitudes of the observed correlation coefficients with the magnitudes of the partial correlation coefficients. Small values of the KMO statistic indicate that the correlations between pairs of variables cannot be explained by other variables and that factor analysis may not be appropriate. For this data the value is 0.833, factor analysis is appropriate for these data (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research - An Applied Approach, 2006)

Table 1:KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.833
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	df
	Sig.
	3298.021
	406
	.000

Total Variance Explained: Table lists the Eigen values associated with each factor before extraction, after extraction and after rotation. First few factors explain relatively large amounts of variance whereas subsequent factors explain only small amount of variance. The first twenty eight components with Eigen values more than 1 have been extracted which define 74.643 % of variance. Principal Component analysis has been used for extraction in the study. Principal components analysis is recommended when the primary concern is to determine the minimum number of factors that will account for maximum variance in the data for use in subsequent multivariate analysis. The factors so extracted are called principal components.

Table 2:Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.650	22.930	22.930	6.650	22.930	22.930	6.549	22.583	22.583
2	5.315	18.328	41.258	5.315	18.328	41.258	5.327	18.368	40.951
3	3.552	12.247	53.504	3.552	12.247	53.504	2.920	10.070	51.021
4	2.464	8.497	62.002	2.464	8.497	62.002	2.592	8.939	59.961
5	1.986	6.849	68.851	1.986	6.849	68.851	2.446	8.435	68.395
6	1.680	5.792	74.643	1.680	5.792	74.643	1.812	6.248	74.643
7	.882	3.041	77.684						
8	.778	2.682	80.366						
.....
28	.104	.359	99.673						
29	.095	.327	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The *Rotated Component Matrix* shows the factor loadings for each variable under all the extracted components. It helps us to formulate an interpretation of the factors or components by looking for a common thread among the variables that have large loadings for a particular component. The researcher went across each row, and highlighted the factor that each variable loaded most strongly on.

Table 3 :Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
I find the store neat and clean	.797	-.064	.058	-.089	-.081	-.097
I find the style of décor/interiors in the store attractive.	.830	.033	.046	-.182	-.022	-.128
I find appropriate lightning in the store.	.882	-.036	.057	-.034	.075	-.047
I find the in-store displays very attractive.	.924	-.001	.044	.101	.003	.006
I find the colours used in the store well coordinated	.836	.031	-.005	-.005	-.117	-.069
I find the placement of signage in the store at appropriate places.	.836	.074	-.029	-.001	-.032	-.087
I find the window display of the store attractive	.855	.055	-.057	.065	.014	.056
I find the merchandise kept on the racks/shelves easily accessible.	.836	.020	-.074	.065	-.002	.052
I find the salesperson in the store well groomed	.838	.031	.033	.227	.078	.065
I am comfortable with the temperature maintained in the store.	-.079	.023	.072	-.029	.046	.901
I feel comfortable in the temperature maintained	-.072	.035	-.204	-.039	-.008	.885
I can easily move around the store.	-.022	-.055	-.020	.032	.851	.061
I find the store space adequate.	.005	-.039	.045	.018	.872	.216
The fitting rooms in the store are spacious.	-.082	-.158	.104	-.087	.812	-.046
The store has adequate number of fitting rooms.	.033	.116	-.121	-.113	.494	-.246
The salesperson the in the store are welcoming.	-.020	.861	-.003	.020	-.020	.085
The sales personnel give me individual attention.	-.024	.885	-.031	.021	-.058	.040
The sales personnel are courteous to me.	-.040	.890	.033	-.005	.007	.068
The salesperson provides prompt services.	-.022	.847	-.081	.000	-.017	-.048
The sales personnel are able to understand my unique need.	.115	.835	-.043	-.034	.034	-.097
The sales personnel have knowledge about the product/ can explain the product features to me.	.091	.864	.073	.002	-.065	-.013
The sales personnel give me helpful advice.	.027	.884	.048	.006	-.051	.011
Ability of the sales personnel to solve problems or deal with complaints.	.019	.039	.209	.892	-.046	.043
The store offers alteration services to me.	.068	-.022	.094	.917	-.034	-.062
The store has flexible return policies.	.001	-.005	.157	.872	-.055	-.036
The store offers easy payment facilities to me.	-.005	.042	.806	.090	-.025	.015
The store provides fast checkout facilities.	.060	-.012	.801	.065	.034	-.143
Proper security makes me feel safe and secured in the store.	-.085	-.011	.854	.125	.027	.002
The opening hours of the store is convenient for me.	.071	-.022	.842	.166	-.020	.020

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a

a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Reliability Test: To study the reliability of the data collected, reliability test was done on the data collected on Likert Statements. Cronbach’s alpha determines the internal consistency or average correlation of items in a survey instrument to gauge its reliability (Cronbach, 1951). It was tested on all the twenty nine statements selected for the study.

Based on the factor loadings, we think the factors represents are:

Table 4 : Factor Analysis

Factor	Element	Factor Loading	Reliability
1.Store Presentation /Display	I find the store neat and clean	.797	0.951
	I find the style of décor/interiors in the store attractive.	.830	
	I find appropriate lightning in the store.	.882	
	I find the in-store displays very attractive.	.924	

	I find the colours used in the store well-coordinated	.836	
	I find the placement of signage in the store at appropriate places.	.836	
	I find the window display of the store attractive	.855	
	I find the merchandise kept on the racks/shelves easily accessible.	.836	
	I find the salesperson in the store well groomed	.838	
2. Personal Interaction	The salesperson the in the store are welcoming.	.861	0.945
	The sales personnel give me individual attention.	.885	
	The sales personnel are courteous to me.	.890	
	The salesperson provides prompt services.	.847	
	The sales personnel are able to understand my unique need.	.835	
	The sales personnel have knowledge about the product/ can explain the product features to me.	.864	
	The sales personnel give me helpful advice.	.884	
3. Convenient Facilities	The store offers easy payment facilities to me.	.806	0.852
	The store provides fast checkout facilities.	.801	
	Proper security makes me feel safe and secured in the store.	.854	
	The opening hours of the store is convenient for me.	.842	
4. Problem Solving	Ability of the sales personnel to solve problems or deal with complaints.	.892	0.9
	The store offers alteration services to me.	.917	
	The store has flexible return policies.	.872	
5. Store Layout	I can easily move around the store.	.851	0.759
	I find the store space adequate.	.872	
	The fitting rooms in the store are spacious.	.812	
	The store has adequate number of fitting rooms.	.494	
6. Temperature	I am comfortable with the temperature maintained in the store.	.901	0.807.
	I feel no humidity inside the store	.885	

The different factors which have been obtained from factor analysis are Store Presentation/Display, Personal Interaction, Convenient Facilities, Problem Solving, Store Layout and Temperature. As per observation and collection of primary data, the company should focus on working on the factors, keeping the internal weaknesses in mind in order to enhance the retail service quality of the store, thereby enhancing the overall perceptual quality of the brand.

Regression Analysis

Regression is a statistical procedure for analyzing associative relationships between a metric-dependent variable and one or more independent variables. Bivariate regression is a procedure for deriving a mathematical relationship, in the form of an equation, between a single metric dependent variable and a single metric-independent variable. Multivariate regression is a statistical technique that simultaneously develops a mathematical relationship between two or more independent variables and an interval-scaled dependent variable (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research - An Applied Approach, 2006). The main objective of regression analysis is to explain the variation in one variable (called the dependent variable), based on the variation in one or more other variables (called the independent variables) (Nargundkar, 2004).

Influence of Perceptual Quality of Retail Store on Perceptual Quality of the Brand

Table 5:ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	113.987	1	113.987	710.235	.000 ^b
	Residual	23.753	148	.160		
	Total	137.740	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Perceptual Quality Of the Brand

b. Predictors: (Constant), Perceptual Quality of the Store

Ho: F=0 or H1:F≠0

Where F is the Anova statistics.

The significance level of Anova Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis i.e F≠0. Thus, F is desirable. Therefore regression equation is acceptable.

Table 6:Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.333	.149		2.228	.027
	Perceptual Quality of the Store	.904	.034	.910	26.650	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Perceptual Quality Of the Brand

Regression equation:

Perceptual Quality of the brand = 0.333 + 0.904 Perceptual Quality of the Retail Store

Ho=0

The significance value is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore there is a significant relationship between perceptual quality of the retail store and perceptual quality of the brand.

Table 7:Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.910 ^a	.828	.826	.40061

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceptual Quality of the Retail Store

Higher value of R Square, higher is the significance of the independent variable. The value of R Square is 0.828. Therefore, 82.8 % of variation in the perceptual quality of the brand can be explained by the perceptual quality of the retail store, rest 17.2% variation is for other reasons.

Correlation

The value of R indicates the correlation between the two variables. The value of the correlation is 0.910. Therefore the perceptual quality of the store and perceptual quality of the brand are positively and strongly correlated.

Influence of Retail Service Quality Factors on Perceptual Quality of the Retail Store.

Table 8:ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	98.674	6	16.446	57.603	.000 ^b
	Residual	40.826	143	.285		
	Total	139.500	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Perceptual Quality of the Store

b. Predictors: (Constant), Temperature, Store Layout, Problem Solving, Convenient Facilities, Personal Interaction, Store Presentation/Display

Ho: F=0 / H1:F≠0

Where F is the Anova statistics.

The significance level of Anova Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis i.e F≠0. Thus, F is desirable. Therefore regression equation is acceptable.

Table 9: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.300	.044		98.562	.000
	Store Presentation/Display	-.071	.044	-.073	-1.620	.108
	Personal Interaction	-.006	.044	-.007	-.148	.883
	Convenient Facilities	.795	.044	.822	18.165	.000
	Problem Solving	.148	.044	.153	3.381	.001
	Store Layout	.054	.044	.055	1.222	.224
	Temperature	-.013	.044	-.014	-.302	.763

a. Dependent Variable: Perceptual Quality of the Store

Regression equation:

Perceptual Quality of the Retail Store = 4.3 + (-.071) Store Presentation/Display + (-0.006) Personal Interaction + 0.795 Convenient Facilities + 0.148 Problem Solving + 0.054 Store Layout + (-0.013) Temperature

Ho=0

The most significant factors that influence the perceptual quality of the store are convenient facilities and problem solving.

Table 10: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.841 ^a	.707	.695	.53432

a. Predictors: (Constant), Temperature, Store Layout, Problem Solving, Convenient Facilities, Personal Interaction, Store Presentation/Display

Higher value of R Square, higher is the significance of the independent variable. The value of R Square is 0.707. Therefore, 70.7% of variation in the perceptual quality of the brand can be explained by the perceptual quality of the retail store, rest 29.3% variation is for other reasons.

Correlation: The value of R indicates the correlation between the two variables. The value of the correlation is 0.841. Therefore the perceptual quality of the store and retail service quality attributes are positively and strongly correlated.

Influence of Retail Service Quality Factors on Perceptual Quality of the Brand.

Table 11: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	86.772	6	14.462	40.576	.000 ^b
	Residual	50.968	143	.356		
	Total	137.740	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Perceptual Quality Of the Brand

b. Predictors: (Constant), Temperature, Store Layout, Problem Solving, Convenient Facilities, Personal Interaction, Store Presentation/Display

Ho: F=0 or H1:F≠0

Where F is the Anova statistics.

The significance level of Anova Statistics is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis i.e F≠0. Thus, F is desirable. Therefore regression equation is acceptable.

Table12 : Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.220	.049		86.572	.000
Store Presentation/Display	.005	.049	.006	.108	.914
Personal Interaction	-.051	.049	-.053	-1.045	.298
Convenient Facilities	.749	.049	.779	15.314	.000
Problem Solving	.105	.049	.110	2.153	.033
Store Layout	.085	.049	.089	1.745	.083
Temperature	.020	.049	.020	.400	.689

a. Dependent Variable: Perceptual Quality Of the Brand

Regression equation:

Perceptual Quality of the Brand = 4.22 + 0.005 Store Presentation/Display+ (-0.051) Personal Interaction+ 0.749 Convenient Facilities+ 0.105 Problem Solving+ 0.085 Store Layout +0.020 Temperature

The most significant factors that influences the perceptual quality of the brand are convenient facilities and problem solving.

Table 13: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.794 ^a	.630	.614	.59701

a. Predictors: (Constant), Temperature, Store Layout, Problem Solving, Convenient Facilities, Personal Interaction, Store Presentation/Display

Higher value of R Square, higher is the significance of the independent variable. The value of R Square is 0.630. Therefore, 63 % of variation in the perceptual quality of the brand can be explained by the perceptual quality of the retail store, rest 20.6% variation is for other reasons.

So, regression analysis has revealed that convenient facilities and problem solving are the major factors that influence of retail service quality of the store and perceptual quality of the brand. Therefore the company should develop marketing strategies to improve on these factors in order to enhance the overall perceptual quality of the brand. Tie ups with different and upcoming e-wallets may be done to attract customers and enhance sales. Separate counters or separately assigned salesperson for cash and online payments may be maintained to improve ease of making payments , and fast checkout facilities. Launch of an app to make payments by directly scanning the product barcode so that the customers can scan the barcode themselves and pay online without standing in the queue. During peak periods, like durgapuja, facility to make the payment by scanning the product in the app can facilitate easy and fast checkout. Trainings may be given to the sales personnel to solve real time problems effectively efficiently keeping customer satisfaction into consideration. Example, how to deal with angry customers. Efficient and effective alteration facilities with an option of delivering the product at their doorstep on purchase of a sum of amount. Attractive return offers for used products in exchange of buying a new product having cashback offers.

Cluster Analysis

Cluster analysis aims to identify and classify similar entities, based upon the characteristics they possess. It helps the researcher to understand patterns of similarity and difference that reveal naturally occurring groups. Objects in each cluster tend to be similar to each other and dissimilar to objects in the other clusters. Cluster analysis is also called classification analysis(Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research - An Applied Approach, 2006).

Technically, a cluster consists of variables that correlate highly with one another and have comparatively low correlations with variables in other clusters (Kothari, 2004). It is a data reduction tool that creates subgroups that are more manageable than individual datum. Cluster analysis (CA) is an exploratory data analysis tool for organizing observed data (e.g. people, things, events, brands, companies) into meaningful taxonomies, groups, or clusters, based on combinations of factors, which maximizes the similarity of cases within each cluster while maximizing the dissimilarity between groups that are initially unknown (Banerjee & Agarwal, 2013)

Using cluster analysis, a customer 'type' can represent a homogeneous market segment. Identifying their particular needs in that market allows products to be designed with greater precision and direct appeal within the segment. Targeting specific segments is cheaper and more accurate than broad-scale marketing. Customers respond better to segment marketing which addresses their specific needs, leading to increased market share and customer retention. Cluster analysis, like factor analysis, makes no distinction between dependent and independent variables. The entire set of interdependent relationships is examined. Cluster analysis reduces the number of observations or cases by grouping them into a smaller set of clusters.

Technique Adapted: As the researchers don't know the number of groups or clusters that will emerge in our sample and as an optimum solution is sought, a two-stage sequence of analysis occurs as follows:

1. A hierarchical cluster analysis using Ward's method applying squared Euclidean Distance as the distance or similarity measure was carried out. This helped to determine the optimum number of clusters we should work with.
2. In the next stage the hierarchical cluster analysis was rerun with the selected number of clusters, which enabled us to allocate every case in our sample to a particular cluster.

Hierarchical Cluster Analysis: This is the major statistical method for finding relatively homogeneous clusters of cases based on measured characteristics. It starts with each case as a separate cluster, i.e. there are as many clusters as cases, and then combines the clusters sequentially, reducing the number of clusters at each step until only one cluster is left. The clustering method uses the dissimilarities or distances between objects when forming the clusters. The SPSS programme calculates 'distances' between data points in terms of the specified variables.

Ward's Method: This method is distinct from other methods because it uses an analysis of variance approach to evaluate the distances between clusters. In general, this method is very efficient. Cluster membership is assessed by calculating the total sum of squared deviations from the mean of a cluster. The criterion for fusion is that it should produce the smallest possible increase in the error sum of squares. The results start with an agglomeration schedule which provides a solution for every possible number of clusters from 1 to 150 (the number of cases in this study). The column to focus on is the central one which has the heading 'coefficients'. Reading from the bottom upwards, it shows the agglomeration coefficient for one cluster to another.

Table 14: Agglomeration Schedule

Stage	Cluster Combined		Coefficients	Stage Cluster First Appears		Next Stage
	Cluster 1	Cluster 2		Cluster 1	Cluster 2	
1	63	140	5.000	0	0	4
2	101	103	10.500	0	0	73
3	51	52	16.000	0	0	44
4	57	63	21.667	0	1	57
144	1	3	3488.344	141	131	149
.....
145	17	22	3657.748	136	140	147
146	2	9	3842.136	143	142	148
147	17	20	4090.317	145	138	148
148	2	17	5132.758	146	147	149
149	1	2	6225.987	144	148	0

The Change of coefficients is rewritten as in the below mentioned Table15 (as it is not provided on SPSS) it is easier to see the changes in the coefficients as the number of clusters increase. The final column, headed 'Change', enabled the researchers to determine the optimum number of clusters. In this case it is 4 clusters as succeeding clustering add very less changes to distinguishing between cases.

Table 15 :Reformed Agglomeration Table

No of Clusters	Agglomeration Last Step	Coefficient This Step	Change
2	6225.987	5132.758	1093.229
3	5132.758	4090.317	1042.441
4	4090.317	3842.136	248.181
5	3842.136	3657.748	184.388
6	3657.748	3488.344	169.404

K-Means Clustering: This method of clustering is very different from the hierarchical clustering and Ward method, which had been applied previously when there is no prior knowledge of how many clusters there may be or what they are characterized by. This is the type of research question that can be addressed by the k-means clustering algorithm. In this study both the hierarchical and the k-means techniques are used successively. The former (Ward’s method) is used to get some sense of the possible number of clusters and the way they merge as seen from the *dendrogram*. In this study, 4 number of Clusters were deduced. Then the clustering is rerun with only a chosen optimum number in which to place all the cases (k means clustering).

Table 16: Final Cluster Centers

	Cluster			
	1	2	3	4
I find the store neat and clean	3.61	2.27	4.04	2.33
I find the style of décor/interiors in the store attractive.	3.79	2.23	4.00	2.28
I find appropriate lightning in the store.	3.88	2.23	4.14	2.06
I find the in-store displays very attractive.	4.23	2.42	4.22	1.72
I find the colours used in the store well coordinated	4.05	2.31	4.16	2.00
I find the placement of signage in the store at appropriate places.	4.30	2.23	4.22	1.94
I find the window display of the store attractive	4.23	2.12	4.31	1.94
I find the merchandise kept on the racks/shelves easily accessible.	4.07	2.46	4.10	1.94
I find the salesperson in the store well groomed	4.35	2.50	4.10	1.61
I am comfortable with the temperature maintained in the store.	3.61	3.88	3.22	3.72
I feel comfortable in the temperature maintained	3.18	3.35	2.94	3.44
I can easily move around the store.	4.05	4.31	4.10	4.00
I find the store space adequate.	3.58	3.62	3.69	3.61
The fitting rooms in the store are spacious.	3.44	3.96	3.69	3.61
The store has adequate number of fitting rooms.	3.65	3.35	3.51	3.61
The salesperson the in the store are welcoming.	4.35	2.19	2.06	4.33
The sales personnel give me individual attention.	4.40	2.15	2.04	4.33
The sales personnel are courteous to me.	4.49	2.42	2.20	4.61
The salesperson provides prompt services.	4.14	2.08	2.12	4.33
The sales personnel are able to understand my unique need.	4.18	1.96	2.22	4.00
The sales personnel have knowledge about the product/ can explain the product features to me.	4.42	1.85	1.96	4.06
The sales personnel give me helpful advice.	4.44	2.04	1.86	4.44
Ability of the sales personnel to solve problems or deal with complaints.	4.18	4.04	3.88	3.50
The store offers alteration services to me.	4.26	4.12	4.22	3.56
The store has flexible return policies.	4.26	4.15	4.16	3.72
The store offers easy payment facilities to me.	3.75	3.77	3.37	3.50
The store provides fast checkout facilities.	3.63	3.54	3.37	3.17
Proper security makes me feel safe and secured in the store.	4.37	4.54	4.14	4.28
The opening hours of the store is convenient for me.	4.42	4.31	4.20	3.83

It is at this point that clear distinguishing characteristics of the clusters are visible and the Cluster 1 is the most attractive cluster as the market size is the highest (See Table Below). Cluster 1 has 38.%, Cluster 2 has 17.33%, Cluster 3 has 32.66% and Cluster 4 has 12 % of sample size.

Table 17 : Number of Cases in each Cluster

Cluster	1	57.000
	2	26.000
	3	49.000
	4	18.000
Valid		150.000
Missing		.000

Table 18 : Distances between Final Cluster Centers

Cluster	1	2	3	4
1		8.012	6.146	6.538
2	8.012		5.655	6.119
3	6.146	5.655		8.927
4	6.538	6.119	8.927	

The differences between Final Cluster Centres Table, shows the distances between the final cluster centres. Greater distances between clusters mean there are greater dissimilarities. So Cluster 3 & 4 has the highest dissimilarity and Cluster 2 & 3 are the most similar one. The dissimilar cluster groups have been ranked as per the Table:

Table 19: Cluster Distances		
Rank	Distance	Cluster
1	Cluster 3 & 4	8.927
2	Cluster 1 & 2	8.012
3	Cluster 1 & 4	6.538
4	Cluster 1 & 3	6.146
5	Cluster 2 & 4	6.119
6	Cluster 2 & 3	5.655

When cluster memberships are significantly different they can be used as a new grouping variable in other analyses. The significant differences between variables for the clusters suggest the ways in which the clusters differ or on which they are based, the more the difference the more the uniqueness in the segment. This helps the marketers if they want to enter into multiple similar segments with their product lines or can target the next segment in their growth strategy. It is never advisable to cater to multiple dissimilar segments.

Table 20 : ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
I find the store neat and clean	25.430	3	.579	146	43.917	.000
I find the style of décor/interiors in the store attractive.	28.164	3	.655	146	42.968	.000
I find appropriate lightning in the store.	35.853	3	.518	146	69.149	.000
I find the in-store displays very attractive.	47.017	3	.510	146	92.112	.000
I find the colours used in the store well coordinated	38.729	3	.692	146	55.943	.000
I find the placement of signage in the store at appropriate places.	48.271	3	.480	146	100.650	.000
I find the window display of the store attractive	51.177	3	.480	146	106.678	.000
I find the merchandise kept on the racks/shelves easily accessible.	35.853	3	.545	146	65.748	.000
I find the salesperson in the store well groomed	49.030	3	.467	146	104.885	.000
I am comfortable with the temperature maintained in the store.	2.956	3	1.701	146	1.738	.162
I feel comfortable in the temperature maintained	1.590	3	1.845	146	.862	.463
I can easily move around the store.	.474	3	1.102	146	.430	.731
I find the store space adequate.	.120	3	1.498	146	.080	.971
The fitting rooms in the store are spacious.	1.717	3	1.340	146	1.281	.283
The store has adequate number of fitting rooms.	.595	3	1.448	146	.411	.746
The salesperson the in the store are welcoming.	62.819	3	.492	146	127.671	.000
The sales personnel give me individual attention.	66.604	3	.391	146	170.532	.000
The sales personnel are courteous to me.	63.057	3	.430	146	146.531	.000
The salesperson provides prompt services.	54.262	3	.616	146	88.035	.000
The sales personnel are able to understand my unique need.	50.532	3	.711	146	71.118	.000

The sales personnel have knowledge about the product/ can explain the product features to me.	73.484	3	.713	146	103.019	.000
The sales personnel give me helpful advice.	79.566	3	.667	146	119.218	.000
Ability of the sales personnel to solve problems or deal with complaints.	2.307	3	.938	146	2.459	.065
The store offers alteration services to me.	2.459	3	1.196	146	2.056	.109
The store has flexible return policies.	1.344	3	1.279	146	1.051	.372
The store offers easy payment facilities to me.	1.645	3	1.405	146	1.171	.323
The store provides fast checkout facilities.	1.260	3	1.080	146	1.167	.324
Proper security makes me feel safe and secured in the store.	.979	3	.913	146	1.072	.363
The opening hours of the store is convenient for me.	1.656	3	.917	146	1.806	.149

The F tests should be used only for descriptive purposes because the clusters have been chosen to maximize the differences among cases in different clusters. The observed significance levels are not corrected for this and thus cannot be interpreted as tests of the hypothesis that the cluster means are equal.

$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4$, where $\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4$ are the average rating for a statement for cluster 1,2,3,4 respectively, which means, mean rating given by the respondents in 4 clusters are the same.

If the statements having the significance level is less than 0.05, that means we reject the H_0 which means there is significant difference across the cluster. Therefore, the statements having significance value less than 0.05 are taken into consideration for evaluating the primary influential retail service quality attributes for 4 clusters.

Store Attributes	Table 21 : Cluster Attributes			
	Cluster 1- Conscious Shoppers	Cluster 2-Casual Shoppers	Cluster 3-Décor Conscious Shoppers	Cluster 4-Sales Personnel Service Conscious Shoppers
Store Cleanliness	Moderate influence	Low influence	Very high influence	Low influence
Décor Attractiveness	High influence	Very low influence	Very high influence	Low influence
Appropriate lighting	Very high influence	Low influence	Very high influence	Very low influence
In-Store Display	Very high influence	Low influence	Very high influence	Very low influence
Colour Coordination	High influence	Moderate influence	Very high influence	Low influence
Signage Placement	High influence	Low influence	High influence	Low influence
Window Display	High influence	Very low influence	High influence	Moderate influence
Merchandise Accessibility	Very high influence	Low influence	Very high influence	Very low influence
Salesperson Grooming	Very high influence	Very low influence	Moderate influence	Low influence
Welcoming	Very high influence	Very low influence	Moderate influence	Very high influence
Individual Attention	High influence	Low influence	Moderate influence	Very high influence
Courteous	High influence	Low influence	Moderate influence	Very high influence
Prompt Services	Moderate influence	Low influence	Moderate influence	Very high influence
Understanding Unique Need	Very high influence	Very low influence	Very low influence	High influence
Product Knowledge	Very high influence	Very low influence	Low influence	Very high influence
Helpful Advice	Very high	Low influence	Low influence	Very high influence

	influence		
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Cluster 1 may be defined as *conscious shoppers* who builds an overall perception of the store on the basis of almost all the attributes. Cluster 2 represents *casual shoppers* who have a very casual approach towards shopping and no attribute in particular influences the store’s perception. Cluster 3 represents customers who are *highly décor conscious* and Cluster 4 may be defined as *sales personnel conscious* shoppers who would always want prim and proper service to be offered by the store sales person.

Initially, multiple clusters should be targeted by the marketer. Thus marketing policies can be developed on the basis of 4 different variables. (Kotler & Keller, 2006) suggested that it would be wise for a company to enter one segment at a time. This will help the company to secretly enter different segment without letting the competitors know beforehand. Cluster 2 & 3 are the most similar clusters and thus may be targeted at the same time with a focus of attracting casual shoppers with the help of good décor which hits their impulsive quotient within. Targeting multiple segments for the rest of the clusters is not advisable as the preferences are quite distinct from each other.

Conjoint Analysis

A technique that attempts to determine the relative importance consumers attach to salient attributes and the utilities they attach to the levels of attributes. Conjoint analysis seeks to develop the utility functions describing the utility consumers attach to the levels of each attribute. (Malhotra & Birks, Marketing Research-An Applied Approach, 2006).

Conjoint analysis means constructing and conducting particular experiments among consumers in order to model their decision making process. Respondents were asked to make judgments about the attributes that affect their purchase decisions conjointly, rather than evaluate each attribute individually. Analysis allows finding out which retail attributes create most value to a customer and how customers are likely to react to different product configurations. This information can lead to the creation of optimal value propositions. . Using conjoint analysis, the researchers were able to determine both the relative importance of each attribute as well as which levels of each attribute are most preferred. If the most preferable product is not feasible for some reason, such as cost, the marketer can know the next most preferred alternative.

The Full-Profile Approach: Conjoint uses the full-profile (also known as full-concept) approach, where respondents rank, order, or score a set of profiles, or cards, according to preference. Each profile describes a complete product or service and consists of a different combination of factor levels for all factors (attributes) of interest.

An Orthogonal Array: The full-profile approach uses fractional factorial design, which presents a suitable fraction of all possible combinations of the factor levels. The resulting set, called an orthogonal array, is designed to capture the main effects for each factor level. Interactions between levels of one factor with levels of another factor are assumed to be negligible. It also to generate factor-level combinations, known as holdout cases, which are rated by the subjects but are not used to build the preference model. But for this study, as the combination of retail attributes are limited the holdout cases are nil and have used only regular plan cases.

The Experimental Stimuli: Each set of factor levels in an orthogonal design represents a different version under study and is presented to the respondents in the form of an individual retail attribute profile. The stimuli is been standardized by making sure that the profiles are all similar in physical appearance except for the different combinations of features. The aim of the study was to understand the influence of three factors on consumer preference for store outlet/format, assistance and exclusive range. These three factors were chosen on the basis of a pilot study conducted by the researchers for the study.

Thus an orthogonal array is generated- that comprises of eight profiles; this orthogonal array was presented to respondents. The respondents ranked the profiles on the basis of preference.

Table 22: Orthogonal Design

Options	Outlet/Format	Assistance	Exclusive Range
1	Exclusive Brand Outlet	Salesperson Assistance	Available
2	Exclusive Brand Outlet	Salesperson Assistance	Unavailable
3	Exclusive Brand Outlet	Self- Assistance	Available
4	Exclusive Brand Outlet	Self- Assistance	Unavailable
5	Multiple Brand Outlet/ Large Format Retail Store	Salesperson Assistance	Available
6	Multiple Brand Outlet/	Salesperson Assistance	Unavailable

	Large Format Retail Store		
7	Multiple Brand Outlet/ Large Format Retail Store	Self- Assistance	Available
8	Multiple Brand Outlet/ Large Format Retail Store	Self- Assistance	Unavailable

This table shows the utility (part-worth) scores and their standard errors for each factor level. Higher utility values indicate greater preference. Since the utilities are all expressed in a common unit, they can be added together to give the total utility of any combination.

Table 23 :Utilities

		Utility Estimate	Std. Error
Outlet	Exclusive Brand Outlet	-.508	.609
	Multi-Brand Outlet/Large Format Retail Store	.508	.609
Assistance	Salesperson Assistance	.017	1.217
	Self Assistance	.033	2.435
Exclusive Range	Available	-.017	1.217
	Unavailable	-.033	2.435
(Constant)		4.500	2.653

The total utility for the eight profiles are given as:

Profile 1: Utility (Exclusive Brand Outlet) + utility (Salesperson Assistance) + utility (Available) +constant = 3.992

Profile 2: Utility (Exclusive Brand Outlet) + utility (Salesperson Assistance) + utility (Unavailable) +constant = 3.976

Profile 3: Utility (Exclusive Brand Outlet) + utility (Self Assistance) + utility (Available) +constant = 4.305

Profile 4: Utility (Exclusive Brand Outlet) + utility (Self Assistance) + utility (unavailable) +constant = 3.992

Profile 5: Utility (Multibrand Outlet/Large Format Retail Store) + utility (Salesperson Assistance) + utility (Available) +constant = 5.008

Profile 6: Utility (Multibrand Outlet/Large Format Retail Store) + utility (Salesperson Assistance) + utility (Unavailable) +constant = 4.992

Profile 7: Utility (Multibrand Outlet/Large Format Retail Store) + utility (Self Assistance) + utility (Available) +constant = 5.024

Profile 8: Utility (Multibrand Outlet/Large Format Retail Store) + utility (Self Assistance) + utility (unavailable) +constant = 5.008

Since *Profile 7* has the highest utility, we can conclude that this is the most desirable combination for the respondent.

Table 24 :Importance Values

Outlet	37.703
Assistance	32.078
Exclusive Range	24.220

Averaged Importance Score

The range of the utility values (highest to lowest) for each factor provides a measure of how important the factor was to overall preference. Factors with greater utility ranges play a more significant role than those with smaller ranges. The results show that Type of retail outlet has the most influence on overall preference. The results also show that exclusive range plays the least important role in determining overall preference. Assistance plays a significant role but not as significant as outlet.

Table 25 : Coefficients

	B Coefficient
	Estimate
Assistance	.017
Exclusive Range	-.017

Coefficients: The regression equation is given as:

$$Y = bX$$

$$Y = 0.017X + (-0.017X)$$

Y is the dependent variable, and X is the independent variable (assistance and exclusive range). This table shows the linear regression coefficients for those factors specified as LINEAR.

Table 26: Correlations^a

	Value	Sig.
Pearson's R	.385	.173
Kendall's tau	.222	.225

a. Correlations between observed and estimated preferences

The above table displays two statistics, Pearson's R and Kendall's tau, which provide measures of the correlation between the observed and estimated preferences. The researchers observed a weak/low correlation between the observed and estimated preferences. Thus, conjoint analysis helps to determine the retail store attribute strategy for the brand which can help it in maximizing the profits.

The marketers should focus more on the type of outlet offered to the customers to enhance their retail experience. Since the customers prefer Multiple Brand Outlets over other formats, the marketers may think of expanding its business by increasing the number of multiple brand outlets. Also, merchandise variety and price points may be increased as it might be one of the reasons for such a preference. In the study, it has been concluded by the researcher that customer service is one of the determinants that affects the buying pattern of the customers and consists of major elements like prompt service, attention given by the sales personnel, courteousness and knowledge of the sales personnel (Singh, Katiyar, & Verma, 2014). The assistance provided to the customers also play an important role so in order to enhance the experience of the customers with the salesperson trainings in regular intervals can be provided to the sales personnel to improve customer satisfaction.

VI. Conclusion and Discussion

In the study the researcher tried to cover up the present scenario of fashion retail service quality, which is one of the growing and popular segments affecting the consumer behaviourism in the apparel market. Five point Likert Scale with a rating was used on 30 statements. The validity test was conduct to test the construct validity with the help of expert opinion. Exploratory factor analysis was run to understand the retail service quality factors in fashion retail market with relevance to the brand, Moustache. Six components were extracted through Varimax method and rotated component matrix, namely *store presentation/display, convenient facilities, problem solving, temperature, store layout and personal interaction*. The reliability of the responses has been checked through Cronback's Alpha. Regression analysis has revealed that there is a significant relationship between perceptual quality of the retail store and perceptual quality of the brand. Convenient facilities and problem solving are the most significant factors that influences the retail service quality of the store and perceptual quality of the brand.

Cluster analysis was done first by hierarchical method to deduce number of clusters which can be formed, and then the data was further processed through Ward Method in K-Means Cluster Method. Four differentiating segment namely, *conscious shoppers, décorconscious, casual shoppers and salesperson conscious shoppers* were concluded with discrete characteristics. The study tried to give a logical insight about the fashion retail customers to the marketers.

Conjoint analysis was done to understand the influence of three factors on consumer preference for store outlet/format, assistance and exclusive range. The result indicated that Type of retail outlet has the most influence on overall preference. Type of retail outlet has the most influence on overall preference having the highest utility value while the exclusive range plays the least important role in determining overall preference. Assistance plays a significant role but not as significant as outlet.

It was also been found out that exclusive range plays the least important role in determining overall preference. Assistance plays a significant role but not as significant as outlet. Hence, a marketer can develop an appropriate strategy to meet the needs of this preference. Perceptual positioning of the brand, Moustache in reference to its competitors based on two dimensions namely, variety and availability. Significant relationship between perceptual quality of the retail store and perceptual quality of the brand has been established. The most significant factors influence the perceptual quality of the retail store and perceptual quality of the brand are convenient facilities and problem solving factor.

The different factors which have been extracted from factor analysis are Store Presentation/ Display, Personal Interaction, Convenient Facilities, Problem Solving, Store Layout and Temperature on which the company should work on in order to improve the retail service quality of the store and overall perceptual quality of the brand. The marketers

may develop marketing strategies to improve on convenient facilities and problem solving factor in order to enhance the overall perceptual quality of the brand. Tie ups with e-wallets may be done to attract customers and enhance sales. Separate counters or separately assigned salesperson for cash and online payments may be maintained to improve ease of making payments, and fast checkout facilities. Launch of an app to make payments by directly scanning the product barcode so that the customers can scan the barcode themselves and pay online without standing in the queue thereby leading to fast checkout. Trainings may be given to the sales personnel to solve real time problems effectively efficiently keeping customer satisfaction into consideration. Efficient and effective alteration facilities and campaigns for attractive return offers on used products may be initiated. Cluster 2 & 3 are the most similar clusters and thus may be targeted at the same time with a focus of attracting casual shoppers with the help of good décor which hits their impulsive quotient within. Targeting multiple segments for the rest of the clusters is not advisable as the preferences are quite distinct from each other. Keeping the internal weaknesses in mind, the company should work on these factors in order to enhance the retail service quality of the store, thereby enhancing the overall perceptual quality of the brand. The marketers may think of expanding its business by increasing the number of multiple brand outlets and merchandise variety and price points may be increased as it might be one of the reasons for such a preference. In order to enhance the experience of the customers with the salesperson trainings in regular intervals can be provided to the sales personnel to improve customer satisfaction as the assistance provided to the customers also play an important role.

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